

A. A short summary of the current design of the EMB of Federal Republic of Nigeria

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) was established by the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria to among other things organize elections into various political offices in the country. The functions of INEC as contained in Section 15, Part 1 of the Third Schedule of the 1999 Constitution (As Amended) and Section 2 of the Electoral Act 2010 (As Amended) include Organize, undertake and supervise all elections to the offices of the President and Vice-President, the Governor and Deputy Governor of a State, and to the membership of the Senate, the House of Representatives and the House of Assembly of each state of the federation; Register political parties in accordance with the provisions of the constitution and Act of the National Assembly; Monitor the organization and operation of the political parties, including their finances; conventions, congresses and party primaries. Arrange for the annual examination and auditing of the funds and accounts of political parties, and publish a report on such examination and audit for public information; Arrange and conduct the registration of persons qualified to vote and prepare, maintain and revise the register of voters for the purpose of any election under this constitution; Monitor political campaigns and provide rules and regulations which shall govern the political parties; Conduct voter and civic education; Promote knowledge of sound democratic election processes; and Conduct any referendum required to be conducted pursuant to the provision of the 1999 Constitution or any other law or Act of the National Assembly.^[1] thus one or another in the shoulder of INEC conduct elections, certify or nullify election results, resolve election disputes, initiate secondary legislation, make regulations or issue proclamations, whether it can determine the election date, draw up an election schedule and issue the election writ, call a by-election, call a general election, power to order re-polling if an election did not proceed in an honest and fair manner as defined in the law, order a re-poll in the event of violence or an emergency, investigate and, where appropriate, prosecute violations of electoral laws & investigate and resolve disputes of an administrative nature or disputes which do not necessarily fall within the jurisdiction of the courts responsibility carried on.

Sections 197 – 205 of the Constitution also provide for the establishment of State Independent Electoral Commission (SIEC) for each state of the federation. INEC has its Headquarters in Abuja, with offices in the capital cities of the thirty-six (36) States, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) as well as in the 774 Local Government Areas in the country. According to section 14, Part 1 of the Third Schedule of the 1999 Constitution, INEC shall comprise the following members:- A Chairman, who shall be the Chief Executive officer; and - Twelve other members to be known as National Electoral Commissioners. Section 14 also stipulates that the Chairman and the National Electoral Commissioner shall be persons of unquestionable integrity; and shall not be less than 50

years and 40 years respectively. The Constitution also provides for the appointment of a Resident Electoral Commissioner for each State of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. Respectively. The Constitution also provides for the appointment of a Resident Electoral Commissioner for each State of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. At the organizational structure of INEC is the Chairman who serves as the Chief Executive Officer of the Commission; who together with the 12 National Electoral Commissioners constitutes the policy-making organ. The Nigerian President had the power to appoint someone from the ranks of Federal Permanent Secretaries to serve as the Secretary to the Commission. ^[2] Such an individual is also usually the Accounting Officer and Head of the Secretariat. In June 2005 a key institution within INEC-The Electoral Institute (TEI) was established for the purpose of the following objectives: 1. Facilitate capacity building and professionalism in the commission through training and manpower development of the commission's staff. 2. Engage in vigorous voter education activities with a view to achieving an increased and effective participation of the electorate in the electoral process. 3. Carry out electoral research and documentation. ^[3]

B. Financial Accountability, Stakeholders & Five Questions to Posed in Federal Republic of Nigeria

In terms of financial accountability, the commission's budget is presented to the relevant committees of the National Assembly. It is also mandated to report to the office of the auditor general at the end of the year. In the procurement of election materials, it is expected to comply with due process requirements through the Bureau of Monitoring, Prices and Intelligence Unit (BMPIU). Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) of federal republic of Nigeria is responsible for effectively using financial resource to achieve the strategical objectives. On the other hand is accountable for effective use of resources, compliance with rules and regulation and ethical financial practices. To stake holders the following questions will be posed includes is INEC subcommittee that oversees its finance set? Is there formal financial reporting structure on hand, is the use of performance budgeting in practice, is regular internal audits has been done? And is there additional audits in case of corrupt or illegal practices. Generally the National Assembly has oversight functions over the commission in the performance of its mandate. While there is no mandatory reporting chain between the commission and the relevant committees of the National Assembly, it reports to these committees when it is requested to do so. As part of its public accountability procedures, the commission also issues periodic reports of its activities to the public. ^[4]

C. Rationale for Reform & the Model the EMB Will Follow in Federal Republic of Nigeria

When all is said and done, restructuring and re-organising the electoral framework is only a small part of the bigger challenge that Nigeria faces. The democratic environment in Nigeria needs to be reformed because, generally, Nigerians do not have much confidence in the elections, umpired by an Electoral Management Body that is in the pocket of the ruling political party. There has to be an attitudinal change amongst political stakeholders. A new electoral mindset has to emerge. Nigerians must stop seeing elections as something that must be won at all costs. ^[5]

There are two crucial areas in the structure of INEC which compromises its independence; with implications for the electoral administrative process and the sustainability of democracy in Nigeria. These are: the method of constituting the electoral management team (commissioners) and the funding of INEC. There are two methods of determining the profile of members of electoral commissions. The first option involves appointing only members who are not partisan or politically inclined, while the second option involves the appointment of people on the basis of their political affiliation. In the appointment of electoral commissioners Section 154 (1) of the 1999 constitution of Nigeria empowers the President to appoint the chairman and commissioners of INEC subject to the confirmation by the senate. Although this provision was not operational in the 1999 elections, the provision as gathered from interviews of political party officials and the transition monitoring group (TMG - a coalition of over 50 civil society organizations and human rights groups involved in election observation in Nigeria) ensured that former President Olusegun Obasanjo appointed members of his political party -the PDP as commissioners; who served in the electoral commission during the conduct of the 2003, 2007 and even to the 2011 Presidential elections. The TMG in particular; maintained that most of the national commissioners and particularly, the resident electoral commissioners (REC's) were nominated by PDP governors from their respective states. Indeed, this problem is compounded by section 156 (1) of the 1999 constitution of Nigeria which states that no person shall be qualified to be a member of INEC if he is not qualified or if he is disqualified for election as a member of the house of representatives Nigeria's election administration system does not conform to the independent model, the governmental model or the mixed model. In fact, there is either, an apparent confusion as to which model of election administration to operate in Nigeria or a deliberate complication of the structure of the election administration system in the country. While INEC is presented and labeled as an "independent body" it has in reality been constituted as an extension of

the executive. Facts on the other hand corroborates this. For example it was observed in all the INEC offices visited across Nigeria that the official vehicles of INEC; including the Toyota land cruiser jeeps of the commissioners were tagged “Presidency”.^[6] Thus, to what extent can INEC be independent when even its logistics is tied to the executive? Furthermore, it will be noticed that there are other institutions controlled directly by the executive which play important roles in the electoral administration process. The police for example provide security; while the ministry of information and the national orientation agency play important roles particularly in the area of voter education. Civil society organizations also play important roles in the area of voter education in Nigerians election administration process. However, more worrisome is the role played by political parties (through state governors and local government chairmen) in the electoral administration process. Political parties in Nigeria are not members of the management team of INEC; yet, apart from being subordinated to the electoral administration process, political parties and candidates also play a part in the administration of elections in Nigeria.^[7] Thus it’s still burning issue and its basis of the Rationale for Reform & the Model the EMB in Federal Republic of Nigeria in the area of making the model that is independent method of constituting the electoral management team (commissioners) and the funding of INEC.

D. Five Recommendations for the Redesign of Federal Republic of Nigeria EMB

1. In essence, the neutrality expected of the electoral commission may take two forms: I. Either a deliberate consideration of the political dimension; with the risk of partiality which is expected to be averted through a balanced representation of political forces; or II. An exclusion, in principle of any political consideration, which is manifested not only in the exclusion of political parties in the selection of the members of the commission, but also in the demand for non-partisan affiliation of members to be appointed into the commission. INEC Chairman should not be appointed by the President, so that he does not have to keep on looking over his shoulders. The mode of appointment of the commission must be abolish.
2. Beyond its financial independence, the constitution must provides security of tenure for the commission by providing for the removal of its members (on the basis of misconduct or an inability to perform the duties of office) by proposing and getting supported by a majority of the senate.

3. **The concerns of qualifications for membership of the commission must be address clearly that the issue by stating that persons appointed into the commission should not be members of political parties which currently is gray area for interpretation .**
 4. **Protects the commission from undue influence from the executive by making Resident Electoral Commissioners accountable to the commission and empowering the commission to appoint and discipline its staff and secretary.**
 5. **Last but not least the structural challenge of Nigeria’s election administration system has to be clarified and must conveniently fit into any of the three main models of EMB’s (that is the independent, governmental or mixed model).**
- E. Three Recommendations for staff retention strategy to identify and keep motivated and competent staff**
1. **Employee engagement, organizational commitment, empowerment of employees, rewards and compensation training and development, communication, management, leadership, use of better selection strategies and utilization of information collected during interviews.**
 2. **Use Newer forms of managerial selection include the use of biographical data, structured interviews, assessment centers, cognitive tests, interest inventories, honesty tests and realistic job previews.**
 3. **Introducing an organizational structure that facilitates smooth staff progression, promotion of staff welfare programs, introduction of incentives such as including senior with honesty.**

Reference List

1. About INEC. INEC Nigeria. (n.d.). Retrieved December 19, 2021, from <https://www.inecnigeria.org/home/about-inec/>
2. Hounkpe .M and Fall .I. M. (2011), Electoral Commissions in West Africa: A Comparative Study, Published by Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, Abuja Regional Office.
3. Ibrahim J. and Garuba .D (2010), A Study of the Independent National Electoral Commission of Nigeria, CODESRIA, Dakar
4. Nigeria: Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) —. (n.d.). ACE. Retrieved December 15, 2022, from <https://aceproject.org/ace-en/topics/em/annex/electoral-management-case-studies/nigeria-a-need-for-modernization>

5. The tragedy of the umpire: the electoral management body and Nigeria's 2019 general elections. (n.d.). Taylor & Francis. Retrieved December 19, 2021, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00358533.2020.1788754>
6. Olaniyi, J. O. (2017, November 27). State Independent Electoral Commissions and local government elections in Nigeria | Olaniyi | Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review. Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review. <https://apsdpr.org/index.php/apsdpr/article/view/133/246>
7. Nigeria: The politicisation of election management bodies comes at a high cost to democracy and must stop | Nelson Mandela School of Public Governance. (n.d.). University of Cape Town. Retrieved December 19, 2021, from <http://www.mandelaschool.uct.ac.za/news/nigeria-politicisation-election-management-bodies-comes-high-cost-democracy-and-must-stop>